

CIS AND TRANS ISOMERISM OF β -ARYLGLUTACONIC ACIDS AND
THEIR DERIVATIVES. PART I. FORMATION OF THE
CIS AND TRANS FORMS OF β -COUMARYL-3- β -
(4-METHOXYPHENYL)-ACRYLIC ACID

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β -Arylglutaconic acids and their derivatives are ordinarily known to exist in the *cis* form. If, however, the esters of these acids are condensed with salicylaldehyde, which contains a hydroxy group, using piperidine as the condensing agent, β -coumaryl-3- β -arylacrylic acid and their esters are obtained in *cis* and *trans* modifications. The present paper deals with the results obtained in the case of β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-, β -(4-methoxy-3 methylphenyl)-, β -(2-methoxy-5 methylphenyl)-, β -(2-methoxy-4 methylphenyl)- and β -(4-methoxy-2 methyl-5 isopropylphenyl)-glutaconic acids.

Dibasic acids containing a double bond are well known to exhibit *cis* and *trans* isomerism as illustrated by the example of maleic and fumaric acids. Substituted and unsubstituted glutaconic acids, which also contain a double bond, might therefore be expected to exist in every case in distinct *cis* and *trans* modifications. But it was found by Perkin and Tattersal (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 361) that although alkyl substituted glutaconic acids could be readily obtained in the *cis* and *trans* forms, the simple unsubstituted glutaconic acid existed only in one form. In the case of β -aryl-substituted glutaconic acids, Thorpe and Bland tried to prepare the *cis* and *trans* forms of β -phenylglutaconic acid, but without success. They observed, however, that when the symmetry of the glutaconic acid molecule was destroyed, as in the case of the semianilides of these acids these derivatives could be obtained in well defined *cis* and *trans* modifications (Thorpe and Bland, *ibid.*, 1912, 101, 862). Before 1931 very few β -aryl-substituted glutaconic acids were known. But after the development of a new method for the preparation of these acids by Linaye and co-workers, several workers have reported the formation of various β -aryl-substituted glutaconic acids and many of their derivatives (Linaye *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1931, 8, 139, 798; *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1934, part II, 140; Gogte, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1934, 1A, 59 *et seq.*). But in all these cases the β -aryl substituted glutaconic acids, and also their derivatives including semianilides have been reported only in one form, which is obviously the *cis* modification, since the above acids readily yield their anhydrides and the derivatives are then prepared from the anhydrides.

It was therefore considered interesting to study the methods and conditions, if any, by which the *trans* modifications of β -arylglutaconic acids or their derivatives could also be obtained. Since the simple semianilides of these acids had already been prepared and were reported only in one form, although their molecules were unsymmetrical, it was thought worthwhile to prepare and study other derivatives of these acids containing unsymmetrical molecules. As β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaconic acid could be prepared readily, it was first selected for this study.

By replacing one of the reactive hydrogen atoms of ethyl β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaconate by a methyl group, followed by hydrolysis, β -(4-methoxyphenyl)- α -methyl-

glutaconic acid was prepared. Though its molecule is unsymmetrical, this acid is found to exist in the *cis* form only as it gives its anhydride (Limaye and Bhave, *Rasayanam*, 1939, 1, 178). Then by the condensation of ethyl β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaconate with benzaldehyde in the presence of sodium ethoxide, followed by hydrolysis, α -benzal- β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaconic acid was prepared (Limaye and Bhave, *loc. cit.*). This again was obtained only in the *cis* form, since it readily gave its anhydride. Thus, it appears that mere symmetrical or unsymmetrical nature of the molecule is not sufficient to ensure that both *cis* and *trans* forms will be formed and isolated. In addition to the unsymmetrical nature of the molecule a new factor, viz., the presence of a hydroxy group in the substituent, has now been introduced by condensing ethyl β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaconate with salicylaldehyde instead of benzaldehyde, in the presence of piperidine. The condensation took place after boiling the alcoholic solution for ten hours. From the reaction mixture in this case, however, two isomeric ethyl esters of the empirical formula $C_{21}H_{18}O_6$ were obtained in almost equal amounts. One of the esters melted at 165° , while the other at 127° . It was also found that if instead of ethyl ester the methyl ester of the glutaconic acid were employed for the condensation, two isomeric methyl esters of empirical formula $C_{20}H_{16}O_6$, one melting at 163° and other at 147° , were obtained. On hydrolysis, both these pairs of isomeric methyl and ethyl esters gave rise respectively to two isomeric acids, one melting at 213° and the other at 198° . Titration results and analysis have shown that both the acids are monobasic and have the formula $C_{19}H_{14}O_6$. By analogy with the formation of the *cis*- α -benzal- β -arylglutaconic acid, mentioned above, and taking into account the results of analysis and combustion, the formation of these esters and acids could be represented by the following scheme with the difference that in this case every compound was obtained in two isomeric forms:—

Since there is no other possibility of formation of isomeric acids of this formula in the condensation, the above acids and esters can be represented as the *cis* and *trans* forms of β -coumaryl-3- β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-acrylic acid and their esters. Further evidence in support of this view was obtained when it was found that by the action of

concentrated sulphuric acid one of the two acids, viz., the acid of m.p. 213° , could be almost quantitatively converted into the other isomeric acid of m.p. 198° , although the reverse change could not be brought about.

The above reaction is found to be of general application and similar *cis* and *trans* forms of the methyl and ethyl esters and of the corresponding substituted acrylic acids can be obtained by condensing the ethyl and methyl esters of the other known β -arylglutaconic acids with salicylaldehyde in the presence of piperidine. The results obtained in the case of the esters of

- (i) β -(4-methoxy-3-methylphenyl)-glutaconic acid,
 - (ii) β -(2-methoxy-5-methylphenyl)-glutaconic acid,
 - (iii) β -(2-methoxy-4-methylphenyl)-glutaconic acid, and
 - (iv) β -(4-methoxy-2-methyl-5-isopropylphenyl)-glutaconic acid
- are detailed in the experimental and the table below.

In the above set of compounds it is now necessary to decide which forms the "cis" and which, the "trans" configuration. The β -arylglutaconic acids employed readily give their anhydrides and they therefore possess the *cis* configuration which may be expected to continue in their esters obtained by Fisher-Spier method. If these esters are condensed with salicylaldehyde in the presence of NaOH or NaOEt under mild conditions of experiment, only one set of products results. These are expected to possess the *cis* form and are shown as such in the experimental, the other set being called the *trans*.

If piperidine is used for this condensation, as mentioned above, both the *cis* and *trans* forms appear.

Further reasons for assigning *cis* and *trans* configuration to particular compounds will be given in a future communication.

It has also been found that if piperidine is used for the condensation of ethyl β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaconate and benzaldehyde then only one form, viz., the *cis* form of the ester is obtained, as is clear from the fact that on hydrolysis of the condensation product, a quantitative yield of the *cis*- α -benzal- β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaconic acid, described by Limaye and Bhawe (*loc. cit.*) which readily gives its anhydride, is obtained. This shows that although the condensing agent, piperidine, is necessary for the appearance of *cis* and *trans* forms, in addition to this, it is necessary to have a group like OH present in the molecule of aldehyde which reacts with one of the COOH groups of the glutaconic acid so as to lock it as by coumarin formation in the present case. Further work in this direction is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Expt. No. 1: Ethyl Ester of the trans- β -Coumaryl-3- β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-acrylic Acid.—The ethyl β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaconate (2.92 g.) (Limaye and Bhawe, *loc. cit.*) was mixed with salicylaldehyde (2 c.c.), and piperidine (0.5 c.c.) and absolute alcohol (5-7 c.c.) added. The solution was boiled under reflux for 10 hours. The solution, which assumed a deep orange colour, was allowed to cool and stand for 3 to 4 hours, when a crop of lemon-yellow crystals was obtained, m.p. $158-60^{\circ}$ (without

decomp.). (The mother-liquor was treated as described below in Expt. No. 4). On crystallisation from ethyl alcohol, shining prismatic crystals of the ethyl ester of the *trans*- β -coumaryl-3- β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-acrylic acid were obtained, m. p. 165° (without decomp.). The ester is insoluble in water; sparingly soluble in benzene, ethyl acetate, alcohol, chloroform and acetic acid, from which it can be crystallised; yield 0.3 g. (Found: C, 71.75; H, 5.33. $C_{21}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 72.0; H, 5.14 per cent).

Expt. No. 2: Methyl Ester of the trans- β Coumaryl-3- β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-acrylic Acid.—This was prepared by using the methyl β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-glutacouate (2.64 g.) in the method described above. The methyl ester of the *trans*- β -coumaryl-3- β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-acrylic acid separated as a crop of yellowish prismatic crystals, m.p. 163° (without decomp.) after crystallisation from methyl or ethyl alcohol. The mother-liquor remaining after the above crop was removed, was further treated as in the Expt. No. 4. The above ester is insoluble in water; sparingly soluble in benzene, ethyl acetate, alcohol, chloroform and acetic acid. (Found: C, 71.18; H, 4.93. $C_{20}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 71.4; H, 4.76 per cent).

Expt. No. 3: trans- β -Coumaryl-3- β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-acrylic Acid.—Any of the esters (1 g.), described above, was dissolved in 1N-alcoholic NaOH (20 c.c.) and the solution was boiled under reflux for 10 hours. A little water was added and the alcohol evaporated off on a water-bath; the solution was diluted with water, filtered and acidified with dilute HCl. The *trans*- β -coumaryl-3- β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-acrylic acid was precipitated as a lemon-yellow solid which was purified by crystallisation from glacial acetic acid or alcohol in light yellow prismatic crystals. The acid is insoluble in water; sparingly soluble in benzene, ethyl acetate, chloroform and ethyl and methyl alcohols, as also acetic acid from which it can be crystallised. After purification it melted at 213° (without decomp.). If 1 g. of the acid of m.p. 213° was dissolved in 10 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid and the solution poured in water after a minute, the acid was quantitatively converted into the *cis* acid of m.p. 198°, described in Expt. No. 4. Its mixed melting point with the *cis*-acid of m.p. 198° (Expt. No. 4) showed a marked depression. The acid of m.p. 213° gave no coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: Equiv., 322.5; C, 70.36; H, 4.69. Monobasic acid $C_{18}H_{14}O_5$ requires equiv., 322; C, 70.80; H, 4.35 per cent).

TABLE I

No.	Substance. Name.	Formula.	M. p.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		Equiv.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1	<i>trans</i> - β -Coumaryl-3- β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-acrylic acid	$C_{19}H_{14}O_5$	213°	70.36	70.80	4.69	4.35	322.5	322.0
2	Ethyl ester of (1)	$C_{21}H_{18}O_5$	165°	71.75	72.00	5.33	5.14	—	—
3	Methyl ester of (1)	$C_{20}H_{18}O_5$	163°	71.18	71.43	4.93	4.76	—	—
4	<i>cis</i> Form of (1)	$C_{18}H_{14}O_5$	198° (decomp.)	70.93	70.80	4.83	4.35	322.5	322.0
5	Ethyl ester of (4)		127°	—	—	—	—	—	—
6	Methyl ester of (4)		147°	—	—	—	—	—	—

TABLE I (contd.)

Name.	Formula.	M. p.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		Rquiv.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
7 <i>trans</i> - β -Coumaryl-3- β -(4-methoxy-3-methylphenyl)-acrylic acid.	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₅	212°	71.04	71.43	4.86	4.76	333.3	336.0
8 Ethyl ester of (7)	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₅	152°	72.13	72.52	5.69	5.49	—	—
9 Methyl ester of (7)		168°	—	—	—	—	—	—
10 <i>cis</i> Form of (7)	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₅	240° (decomp.)	70.96	71.43	4.96	4.76	333.3	336.0
11 Ethyl ester of (10)		150°	—	—	—	—	—	—
12 Methyl ester of (10)		153°	—	—	—	—	—	—
13 <i>trans</i> - β -Coumaryl-3- β -(2-methoxy-5-methylphenyl)-acrylic acid	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₅	200°	70.91	71.43	4.9	4.76	333.3	336.0
14 Ethyl ester of (13)	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₅	120°	72.19	72.52	5.72	5.49	—	—
15 Methyl ester of (13)		147°	—	—	—	—	—	—
16 <i>cis</i> Form of (13)	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₅	233° (decomp.)	71.12	71.43	4.88	4.76	333.3	336.0
17 Methyl ester of (16)		153°	—	—	—	—	—	—
18 Ethyl ester of (16)		145°	—	—	—	—	—	—
19 <i>trans</i> - β -Coumaryl-3- β -(2-methoxy-4-methylphenyl)-acrylic acid.	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₅	220°	70.74	71.43	4.87	4.76	333.3	336.0
20 Ethyl ester of (19)	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₅	140°	72.30	72.52	5.63	5.49	—	—
21 Methyl ester of (19)		165°	—	—	—	—	—	—
22 <i>cis</i> Form of (19)	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₅	228° (decomp.)	—	—	—	—	327.8	336.0
23 Methyl ester of (22)		110°	—	—	—	—	—	—
24 <i>trans</i> - β -Coumaryl-3- β -(4-methoxy-2-methyl-5-isopropylphenyl)-acrylic acid.	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₅	172°	72.9	73.10	5.90	5.82	377.3	378.0
25 Ethyl ester of (24)	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₅	125°	73.36	73.80	6.56	6.40	—	—
26 Methyl ester of (24)		147°	—	—	—	—	—	—
27 <i>cis</i> Form of (24)	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₅	150° (decomp.)	73.12	73.01	5.93	5.82	377.3	378.0
28 Methyl ester of (27)	—	158°	—	—	—	—	—	—
29 Ethyl ester of (27)	—	138°	—	—	—	—	—	—

Expt. No. 4: cis- β -Coumaryl-3- β -(4-methylphenyl)-acrylic Acid.—The mother-liquor, referred to in Expts. 1 and 2 above, was transferred to a flask containing

about 100 c.c. of water and was subjected to steam distillation for about 45 minutes, during which most of the unreacted salicylaldehyde passed over in the distillate. The flask was disconnected and its dark brown semi-solid contents and the supernatant solution were allowed to cool. The supernatant liquid was decanted and filtered and the filtrate was acidified with dilute HCl, when a flocculent white precipitate was first obtained. This soon turned into a grey, friable mass, m.p. 180°-190°. This was purified by crystallisation from ethyl alcohol or acetic acid, when white needle-like crystals of the *cis*- β -coumaryl-3- β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-acrylic acid were obtained, m.p. 198° (decomp.). Its mixed melting point with the *trans*-acid of m.p. 213° showed a marked depression. The acid of m.p. 198° is insoluble in water, sparingly soluble in benzene, ethyl acetate, chloroform, ethyl and methyl alcohols and acetic acid from which it could be crystallised. It was found identical with the acid of the same m.p. obtained by the action of sulphuric acid on the *trans*-acid. It gave no coloration with ferric chloride. By the usual Fischer Spier method this acid gave (a) ethyl ester, m.p. 127° (without decomp.) and (b) methyl ester, m.p. 147° (without decomp.) from each of which the acid could be regenerated by hydrolysis. (Found: Equiv., 322.5; C, 70.93; H, 4.83. Monobasic acid $C_{19}H_{16}O_5$ requires equiv., 322.0; C, 70.80; H, 4.35 per cent).

By following a similar procedure (as described in Expt. No. 1 to Expt. No. 3) the esters of the β -arylglutaconic acids were condensed with salicylaldehyde in the presence of piperidine and the various products obtained are listed in Table I.

The above work was carried out in author's laboratory at Dadar, Bombay.

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